
AIRCRAFT AND THEIR MAIN ELEMENTS

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Original article

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Abstract: Currently, UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) have filled a large area of our life: military, civil, space, medical, logistic, etc. In the scientific field, work continues on upgrading existing and developing new drones for more efficient performance of the tasks assigned to the drone. The purpose of this work is to study the use of UAVs (quadcopters), consider its main elements, and construct a mathematical model of a quadcopter.

Keywords: UAV, drone, quadcopter

One of the tasks of UAV control is to ensure flight stability.

When piloting a UAV, there are external influences. The main Influences that interfere with piloting are: gusts of wind, sharp pressure drops, turbulent flows, radio interference, magnetic anomalies, etc.

To stabilize the flight, the drone software uses different types of regulators. The better the regulators are selected and the higher the clock frequency of data processing, the higher the accuracy and stability of control.

There are many types of drones and purposes for using them. Drones differ in the number of rotors used and their location. Also, the selection of components is greatly affected by whether the drone will be high-speed, cargo or combined. Drones designed for flights at high speeds have their own distinctive features. Such drones should be small in size to minimize air resistance. The motors must have a high KV value (the number of revolutions per volt). The battery is selected as light as possible, without compromising its high current output. The higher the current output, the more powerful the motors that can be used. The flight duration of such drones is not long, about 3-10 minutes. Drones intended for video filming or cargo delivery must

have a large thrust reserve. For such drones, motors with a low KV value are used. are selected with an increased angle of attack to increase thrust. Batteries are selected high-voltage with an average current output, but a large capacity.

However, the larger the capacity does not mean that the drone will fly longer.

It is necessary to find a golden mean when selecting components.

A drone (quadcopter) is a complex device consisting of numerous components. In turn, the components are divided into primary and additional. The primary ones include flight controllers, power supply system, regulators and motors. Additional

components are determined depending on the specialization of the drone. These include a camera stabilizer, cargo grips, tanks and various brackets.

Main elements:

Flight controller. The main element, without which no quadcopter can be imagined, is the flight controller. The role of the flight controller can be played by both ready-to-install boards and any hardware platforms with a microprocessor. The flight controller must have a high clock frequency. The more often the flight polling and correction cycle occurs, the more stable the flight will be and the smaller the value errors.

1 -Ready-made flight controller

2-Hardware platform

Motor controller. The motors are connected to the flight controller, but they cannot be connected directly to the controller. ESC controllers are used for this. Such controllers are used to control brushless motors. The controller has several basic characteristics. Nominal and peak power. It characterizes what current output the regulator can provide for one motor for a long time and for a short period of time. Regulators support different batteries. In the characteristics, this is described as $N*s$, where N is the number of parallel-connected battery cells. Each cell produces 3.7 volts. And when the regulator indicates that supports 2-4s batteries, which means that this regulator operates at a voltage of 7.4 – 14.8 volts.

3-Brushless motor

Engine. There are two types of quadcopter engines: brushed and brushless. Brushed engines consist of the following elements: shaft, collector, anchor, brushes, stator. The advantages of this type of engine are: small weight and dimensions, low price, repairability. The disadvantages of this type of engine are:

Brushless motors consist of the following elements: stator, rotor, coils with winding. The advantages of this type of motor are: high rotation speed, wear resistance, resistance to external impacts, higher efficiency compared to collector motors, good cooling, therefore lower temperature, quiet operation, low weight, durability. The disadvantages of this type of motors are: high cost, difficult repair, more expensive regulators.

Fig 1 Coordinate systems and Roll Pitch Yaw angles [5]

3-ESC regulator

$$e(t) = xd(t) - x(t) \quad (1)$$

$$u(t) = KPe(t) + KI \int e(\tau) d\tau + KD \frac{d}{dt} e(t) \quad (2)$$

Mathematical model of an unmanned aerial vehicle with four propulsors (quadcopter) is indispensable in quadcopter movement simulation and later modelling of the control algorithm. Mathematical model is, at the same time, the first step in comprehending the mathematical principles and physical laws which are applied to the quadcopter system. The objective is to define the mathematical model which will describe the quadcopter behavior with satisfactory accuracy and which can be, with certain modifications, applicable for the similar configurations of multirotor aerial vehicles. At the beginning of mathematical model derivation, coordinate systems are defined and explained. By using those coordinate systems, relations between parameters defined in the earth coordinate system and in the body

coordinate system are defined. Further, the quadcopter kinematic is described which enables setting those relations. Also, quadcopter dynamics is used to introduce forces and torques to the model through usage of Newton-Euler method. Final derived equation is Newton's second law in the matrix notation. For the sake of model simplification, hybrid coordinate system is defined, and quadcopter dynamic equations derived with the respect to it. Those equations are implemented in the simulation. Results of behavior of quadcopter mathematical model are graphically shown for four cases. For each of the cases the propellers revolutions per minute (RPM) are set in a way that results in the occurrence of the controllable variables which causes one of four basic quadcopter movements in space.

Currently, a common approach of studying the quadrotor dynamics is simulated using MATLAB/Simulink to verify the flight performance. This paper proposed a method of further analysis and justifications to the current approach, which consists of designing the geometry in SolidWorks followed by using ADAMS for verifications. Based on the studies implemented, the dynamic model has been

theoretically presented for all the six degrees of freedom. Appropriate parameters were identified based on previous studies which includes; quadrotor frame, BLDC motor and the propeller characteristics. From the results attained, it can be concluded that the performance from ADAMS environment has presented similar results to the mathematical model. The software also presented the dynamics as a 3D virtual setting rather than a collection of numerical data from Simulink. However, developing the geometry and running it on ADAMS can be quite complex due to the extensive features that are readily available. Hence, it is vital to ensure that the model is carefully developed and that the dimensions within the geometry are also accurate. Future work will continue to explore ADAMS while using control techniques and modifying the mechanical system. Additionally, carrying out practical developments and comparing the results will also be considered.

Literature

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